

Impact on Retail Marketing Global Era - An Overview (Marketing Channels)

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Introduction

As the 21st century begins to unfold, globalization has become more than just another piece of fancy jargon of the business lexicon. In fact, globalization in the sense of firms from all over the world interacting and dealing with each other is expected to be the normal state of affairs for the majority of businesses. In the industrial or business-to-business sector, this pattern may be even more pronounced because advanced communications and transportation technologies have the potential for enabling the laws of comparative advantage to be realized to a very high degree. Thus, businesses that were used to dealing with other businesses from all over the country will now seek relationships from all over the world. Internet-based B2B E-commerce, has, of course, been at the vanguard of the expected revolution in the way global business will be conducted in the future and has led to uncounted predictions of a worldwide e-business revolution where virtually all industrial firms will be linked together in a gigantic electronic global network. Yet, this scenario seems a bit too simplistic. All of the hype about global B2B E-commerce, networks, hubs, electronic auctions, etc., implies that the only thing standing in the way of electronically linked businesses on a global scale is the right technological hardware and software that, once put in place, will have global businesses operating with the precision and reliability of a Swiss watch. After all, this technocentric view suggests that the only difference between operating around the block or around the world is geographical distance. Therefore, it is just a matter of having the right satellites, telecommunications networks, and supply chains in place to solve this problem of distance.

The purpose of this article is to show that there is more to distance in global business-to-business relationships than mere geography. Distance can also be defined in terms of culture so that one can think of "cultural distance" as a challenge that must be addressed by businesses from different countries around the globe who seek to deal with each other.

Culture and Cultural Distance

In an era of relatively instantaneous contact between organizations across the seemingly shrinking globe, why should one consider cultural distance at all? Simply because culture affects virtually all of human behavior. For example, culture has been defined as “the software of the mind”. Hofstadter’s extensive research on culture has helped conceptualize one of the most popular theories of cultural types, as evidenced by well over 1000 citations from Cultural Consequences reported in the Social Science Citation since 1980. His approach to culture initially identified four underlying value dimensions:

- Individualism vs. collectivism,
- Large vs. small power distance,
- Strong vs. weak uncertainty avoidance, and
- Masculinity vs. femininity (a fifth dimension, long- vs. short-term orientation was added later).

Another framework for the understanding of culture was developed by Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner. It was based on 50,000 cases of managers from multinational and international corporations from over 100 countries. In their approach, cultures differ in the specific solutions they choose to problems. They then identify cultures based on seven fundamental dimensions. Their approach is similar in some respects to Hofstede’s dimensions. While the above approaches are relevant to the development of many types of managerial strategies and tactics, this study is concerned specifically with communication issues. An approach to national culture that was developed by the cultural anthropologist Hall is, thus, appealing in this context. In fact, Hall declared that “culture is communication”. If a person is to communicate effectively with someone from another culture, he/she must be able to “decode” the message properly. Without such a code-breaker, two people from different cultures may see or hear the same message but may screen that message very differently by unconsciously ignoring or increasing the importance of various parts of the message. In addition, one may interpret the message content differently, “seeing” or “hearing” the message so that it is consistent with his or her cultural norms. Both the sender and the receiver of a message are products of their own fields of reference or expertise, that is, the sender has been socialized given his or her own external cultural environment, as has the receiver.

The less these two fields of experience or reference overlap, the more “distant” one person’s cultural background is from another’s, and the more difficult clear communication and understanding is between the two. Hall’s low- (LC) and high-context (HC) dichotomy provides a simple two-category basis for grouping the cultures of many different countries to help understand the hidden codes in communication. In his framework, in LC cultures, most of the information flowing between sender and receiver is contained in the message itself. Consequently, the message needs to be explicit and detailed because each party will rely almost solely on the information contained in the message itself. On the other hand, in an HC culture, less explicit and detailed information is carried in the message itself. Instead, the sender and receiver rely more on the context of the communication process to convey the message. Consequently, the human element and personal relationships tend to play a much larger role in communication in HC cultures.

yet most efforts addressing the importance of communication across cultures have been primarily conceptual. It is accepted that it is an important facet of marketing channels and effective communication in marketing channels is difficult enough to achieve in domestic marketing channels where culture is relatively homogeneous.

Hypotheses

As long as channel members from LC or HC cultures deal with foreign marketing channel partners from similar LC or HC cultures, the cultural distance between the two will be relatively small and, hence, few communication problems based on cultural distance are likely to appear in the marketing channel. However, as is so often the case in international business, marketing channel partners often come from both LC and HC cultures (e.g. the US and Brazil, the US and Japan, the US and Mexico). Thus, the cultural distance may be relatively large and may become a crucial issue in developing an effective and efficient flow of communication in international channels of distribution.

Countries Categorized As Low Context and High Context Low-Context Countries High-Context Countries

- Australia Argentina
- Austria Brazil
- Belgium China
- Britain Israel
- Canada Italy
- France Japan
- Germany Korea
- New Zealand Mexico
- pain
- Turkey

Communication in International Marketing Channels, the following hypotheses are offered:

Hypothesis 1: Fax communication frequency between international channel partners increases when cultural distance is large.

Hypothesis 2: Telephone communication frequency between international channel partners increases when cultural distance is large.

Hypothesis 3: E-mail communication frequency between international channel partners increases when cultural distance is large.

Hypothesis 4: Written communication (business letters) frequency between international channel partners increases when cultural distance is large.

Methodology

To explore the impact of cultural distance on communication in international marketing channels, a study of communication between US exporters and their distributors in foreign countries was undertaken. Since all of the exporters in the study were US-based, by definition they are all LC.

Suggestion

Communication frequency was assessed by asking the export managers to indicate the frequency of their communication with the foreign distributor over a period of 4 weeks.

They provided information about how frequently they contacted the foreign distributor via telephone, fax, e-mail, and written letters. A five-point Likert scale ranging from very infrequently to very frequently was used to measure respondents' perceptions of foreign distributors' contact frequency. These respondents also provided information about how frequently they were contacted by the foreign distributor via telephone, fax, e-mail, and written letters using the same five-point Likert scale ranging from very infrequently to very frequently. Cultural distance was assessed via Hall's HC vs. LC cultural classification.

Findings

In order to provide the highest level of sensitivity possible for measuring respondents’ perception of how frequently they needed to communicate due to cultural distance, only the very frequently category is reported here. By focusing on the exporters’ responses at this very high level of communication frequency, the chance of including what might be considered “normal” everyday communication between the US exporters and their foreign distributors is minimized. The following sections report the findings for communication via fax, telephone, E-mail, and written letters.

Conclusion

Much of the promise of B2B e-commerce on a global scale is dependent upon the efficiency that can theoretically be gained by electronically linked channel participants. Thus, instead of intensive communications between people at all levels of the marketing channel contacting each other to make sure that the right products are moving through international channels at the right place and time, Internet based e-commerce would replace all of these people-centered communication processes. In short, communication among channel participants would be computer-to-computer not person-to-person in the international B2B e-commerce scenario. Once such electronic networks are in place, with the appropriate electronic marketplace architecture and B2B software, smooth and continuous flows of products from any given country to another would occur “automatically” based on virtually perfect flows of communication through the electronic networks. In such a world, good communication is dependent solely on having the right technology in place to traverse the distances separating channel participants in different countries. Variations among nations, and their peoples stemming from different cultures would be irrelevant in such a scenario. Cultural distance, if it exists, would be erased by the awesome power of the Internet.

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